

Photochemical Reaction between *cyclo*Hexane and Chlorine in Carbon Tetrachloride Solutions.

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Photochemical reactions involving chlorine have always been a fascinating though somewhat puzzling problem to the photo-chemists. To elucidate the action of light on chlorine, the author has already studied the mechanism of an additive reaction involving chlorine in solution *viz.* the photochemical reaction between cinnamic acid and chlorine (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 341). In this communication the results of the study of a substitution reaction involving chlorine—the photochemical action of chlorine on *cyclo*hexane—will be described. The previous paper should be referred to for information about the purification of solvent, preparation of chlorine and other details.

The chlorination of *cyclo*hexane has not been studied by any previous investigator. The photo-bromination of *cyclo*hexane vapour has been studied by Pusch (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1918, 24, 336), Noddack (*ibid*, 1921, 27, 359) and recently by Wood and Rideal (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 131, 2466). Pusch and Noddack found the quantum efficiency of the reaction to be unity, and wood and Rideal find that the reaction gives unimolecular constants unaffected by changes in temperature or concentration of the acceptor and directly proportional to the intensity of radiation.

Kahlbaum's *cyclo*hexane was shaken with concentrated sulphuric acid and distilled. The reaction vessel (4 × 4 × 1 cm.) with plane parallel glass sides was placed inside a double jacketted metal box maintained within $\pm 0.1^\circ$ by circulation of water. The reaction-cell had a narrow opening at the top provided with a closely fitting stopper. The reaction was followed by pipetting out 2 c. c. from time to time, and the chlorine determined iodometrically with *N*/200-sodium thio-sulphate which was prepared afresh, and standardised before each experiment.

The Dark Reaction.

In perfectly dry carbon tetrachloride solutions, the reaction between *cyclo*hexane and chlorine in the dark was, as Table I will show, negligible at 27°.

TABLE I.

The Dark Reaction.

*cyclo*Hexane = M/3. Chlorine = M/69. Temp. = 27°.

Time in mins.	N/200-Thiosulphate.	Unimol. const. log $a/(a-x)$.
0	11'60 c. c.	—
45	11'55	0'0000422
141	11'45	0'0000404
231	11'35	0'0000411
321	11'30	0'0000347
441	11'20	0'0000347
		Mean 0'0000336

On raising the temperature to 32° the mean unimolecular constant for the dark reaction was found to be 0'000044.

The reaction proceeded fairly quickly under stimulus of radiation from a quartz mercury lamp run from a storage battery under a constant current of three amperes. The kinetics of the reaction was studied in white light, the reaction cell being at a distance of 25 cm. and a water-filter, 4 cm. thick being placed between. As the following tables will show the reaction with an excess of *cyclo*hexane gave a unimolecular constant with respect to chlorine, the constant showing a tendency to fall off towards the end of the reaction.

With excess of *cyclo*hexane the reaction proceeded till the chlorine completely disappeared. As it was not possible to estimate the *cyclo*hexane along with chlorine one cannot definitely say how many molecules of chlorine ultimately reacted with a molecule of *cyclo*hexane when excess of the latter was employed. With an initial concentration of chlorine about double that of *cyclo*hexane, it was found that the completion of the reaction corresponded to about three atoms of chlorine reacting with one molecule of *cyclo*hexane.

In this investigation an excess of *cyclo*hexane was always employed. Under such conditions the reaction rate was found to be unimolecular with respect to chlorine showing that the reaction mainly consisted in the formation of the monochloro-substitution product. The value of the unimolecular constant showed a tendency to diminish as the reaction progressed. This point will be discussed later on.

Tables II-V indicate the typical results, while Table VI summarises the results at different concentrations of *cyclohexane* and chlorine. The temperature was 27.8° throughout. The unimolecular constants are all on the basis of logarithm to the base 10 and time is reckoned in minutes.

TABLE II.

	<i>cycloHexane</i> = M/3.			Chlorine = M/60.		
Time (mins.)...	0	10	25	40	65	85
N/200-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ ...	12.85	11.25	9.4	7.9	6.1	5.0 c.c.
Unimol. const. ...	—	0.00578	0.00543	0.00529	0.00498	0.00482
						Mean—0.00510.

TABLE III.

	<i>cycloHexane</i> = M/3.			Chlorine = M/46.		
Time (mins.) ...	0	10	25	45	70	115
N/200-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ ..	17.4	15.25	12.75	10.25	8.15	5.55 c.c.
Unimol. const. ...	—	0.00573	0.00540	0.00511	0.00470	0.00431
						Mean—0.00505

TABLE IV.

	<i>cycloHexane</i> = M/30.			Chlorine = M/30.		
Time (mins.)	0	10	25	40	60	92
N/200-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ ...	13.35	11.95	10.35	8.9	7.45	5.65 c.c.
Unimol. const. ...	—	0.00481	0.00442	0.00440	0.00422	0.00406
						Mean—0.00438

TABLE V.

	<i>cycloHexane</i> = M/1.5.			Chlorine = M/65.		
Time (mins.) ...	0	10	25	45	67	90
N/200-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ ...	12.1	10.0	7.85	6.0	4.55	3.6 c.c.
Unimol. const. ...	—	0.00828	0.00752	0.00677	0.00634	0.00585
						Mean—0.00695

TABLE VI.

Conc. of <i>cyclohexane</i> .	Conc. of chlorine.	Mean unimol. const.
M/1.5	M/65	0.00695
M/3	M/60	0.00510
M/7.5	M/60	0.00468
M/36	M/60	0.00438
M/37.5	M/60	0.00388
M/3	M/108	0.00443
M/3	M/76	0.00430
M/3	M/63	0.00510
M/3	M/46	0.00505

It will be seen from above that similar to the observations of Wood and Rideal on the bromination of *cyclohexane* vapour (*loc. cit.*), the unimolecular constant is practically independent of the initial concentration of chlorine. The unimolecular constant, however, continually increases as the concentration of the acceptor (*cyclohexane*) increases.

Wood and Rideal maintain that in the bromination of *cyclohexane* the unimolecular constant is independent of the initial concentration of the acceptor. A consideration of their values reproduced in Table VI (A) at once shows that the unimolecular constant distinctly increases slowly with increase in concentration of the acceptor if we only omit the value for *cyclohexane* vapour pressure of 3.93 cm.

TABLE VI (A).

<i>cycloHexane</i> vapour pressure.	Bromine vapour pressure.	$K \times 10^4$.	<i>cycloHexane</i> vapour pressure.	Bromine vapour pressure.	$K \times 10^4$.
7.13 cm.	2.10 cm.	198	3.93 cm.	1.79 cm.	187
6.10	2.01	186	3.12	1.53	178
5.24	2.25	182	2.11	1.96	161

Effect of Hydrochloric Acid.—It will be observed that the unimolecular constant with respect to chlorine has a tendency to diminish as the reaction proceeds. It was thought that the hydrochloric acid generated in the reaction might have a retarding action. Experiments were, therefore, carried out in the presence of hydrochloric acid. Hydrochloric acid generated by the action of pure concentrated sulphuric acid on pure concentrated hydrochloric acid was washed successively through water, sulphuric acid and carbon tetrachloride and then dissolved in carbon tetrachloride. Tables VII and VIII will indicate that hydrochloric acid has no retarding effect but a very slight accelerating effect.

TABLE VII.

cycloHexane = M/3. Chlorine = M/60. HCl = M/55.5. Temp. = 20°.

Time in mins.	...	0	11	25	40	60	80
N/300-Thiosulphate...	13.25		11.45	9.55	7.85	6.10	4.95 c.c.
Unimol. const.	...	—	0.00576	0.00569	0.00568	0.00562	0.00535

Mean—0.00562

TABLE VIII.

*cyclo*Hexane = M/3. Chlorine = M/60. HCl = M/18.5. Temp. = 28°.

Time in mins.	...	0	10	25	40	60	87
N/200-Thiosulphate	...	13.0	11.3	9.25	7.55	6.0	4.5 c.c.
Unimol. const.	...	—	0.00608	0.00591	0.00590	0.00560	0.00530

Mean—0.00576

In the absence of hydrochloric acid, the mean value of the unimolecular constant is, from Table II, 0.00510. In the presence of the acid also, the unimolecular constant appears to diminish as the reaction progresses. The effect is, therefore, to be ascribed to the disturbing influence of the other reaction product, *viz.*, the chloro*cyclo*hexane.

Experiments in Monochromatic Light.

The quantum efficiency, temperature coefficient and the influence of intensity of radiation were then determined at wave-lengths 36.5 μ , 40.4 μ and 43.6 μ . The same filters were employed to isolate the different lines as was done in the chlorination of cinnamic acid (*loc. cit.*) with the difference that for the wave-length 43.6 μ the 2 cm. water filter was replaced by a 2 cm. filter of copper sulphate solution (20 gm. in 100 c.c.).

The intensity measurements were carried out with a Moll thermopile and a Moll galvanometer calibrated with a Hefner lamp at a distance of 100 cm.

The following experiments (Tables IX—XI) were carried out at 27°; a lower temperature could not be employed as further lowering of the temperature resulted in the deposition of moisture on the reaction vessel.

TABLE IX.

Intensity of incident radiation = 1.3 Hefners—at—100 cm.

Wave-length = 43.6 μ . *cyclo*Hexane = M/3. Chlorine = M/65.
Temp. = 27°.

Time in mins.	...	0	15	35	60	86	110
N/200-Thiosulphate	...	12.4	11.6	10.7	9.5	8.7	8.0 c.c.
Unimol. const.	...	—	0.00193	0.00183	0.00193	0.00179	0.00173

Mean—0.00184

Subtracting the dark reaction, the true light reaction is 0.00180.

TABLE X.

Intensity of incident radiation = 0.18 Hefners—at—100 cm.

Wave-length = 404 $\mu\mu$. *cyclo*Hexane = M/3. Chlorine = M/66.
Temp. = 27°.

Time in mins.	...	0	15	45	90	150	208
N/200-Thiosulphate	...	12.1	11.8	11.3	10.8	10.0	9.5 c.c.
Unimol. const.	...	—	0.000727	0.000660	0.000549	0.000552	0.000510

Mean—0.000600

The light reaction constant is thus 0.000561.

TABLE XI.

Intensity of incident radiation = 0.11 Hefners—at—100 cm.

Wave-length = 366 $\mu\mu$. *cyclo*Hexane = M/3. Chlorine = M/60.
Temp. = 27°.

Time in mins.	...	0	20	46	80	125	185
N/200-Thiosulphate	...	13.05	12.7	12.3	11.9	11.25	10.50 c.c.
Unimol. const.	...	—	0.000585	0.000557	0.000500	0.000515	0.000509

Mean—0.000533

The light reaction constant is 0.000494.

Quantum Efficiency at Various Wave-lengths.—The light absorbed was measured by taking galvanometer readings with the reaction cell filled with the solvent, and with chlorine solution of requisite strength. 1 Mm. of galvanometer deflection corresponded to 9 ergs per sq. cm. per sec.

At 436 $\mu\mu$. The light absorbed corresponded to 18 mm. of galvanometer deflection. No. of quanta absorbed per sq. cm. per sec. therefore

$$= 18 \times 9 \times \frac{436 \times 10^{-7}}{3 \times 10^{10}} \times \frac{1}{6.5 \times 10^{-27}}$$

$$= 3.6 \times 10^{13} \text{ quanta per sq. cm. per sec.}$$

The change in chlorine concentration (Table IX) equals 0.8 c.c. of N/200 in 2 c.c. in 15 mins.

No. of mols. changed per sq. cm. per sec.

$$= \frac{.80}{2} \times \frac{1}{2 \times 2} \times \frac{1}{100} \times \frac{1}{1000} \times \frac{1}{15 \times 60} \times 6.1 \times 10^{23}$$

$$= 6.78 \times 10^{14},$$

∴ The quantum efficiency = 19 mols. per quantum.

At 404 $\mu\mu$. The radiation absorbed was equivalent to 4 mm. No. of quanta absorbed per sq. cm. per sec. = 7.43×10^{12} . Table X shows that the change in chlorine concentration was 0.8 c.c. of N/200 in 2 c.c. in 45 mins.

No. of molecules reacted per sq. cm. per sec. = 22.59×10^{13} .

Hence about 30 molecules reacted per quantum of light absorbed.

At 366 $\mu\mu$. Absorption corresponded to 3 mm. of galvanometer deflection. No. of quanta absorbed per sq. cm. per sec. = 5.067×10^{12} . Chlorine transformed (Table XI) = 0.75 c.c. of N/200 in 2 c.c. in 46 mins. No. of mols. transformed per sq. cm. per sec. = 20.7×10^{13} . Thus about 41 molecules reacted per quantum of radiation absorbed.

The quantum efficiency of this reaction is thus very large. This must be ascribed to a reaction chain set up as a result of absorption of radiation. Quantum efficiency also increases as the frequency of the incident radiation increases.

Temperature Coefficient at different Wave-lengths.

The experiments in monochromatic lights of the same intensity and with the same initial concentrations were then performed at an elevated temperature (32°). The corresponding velocity constant for the dark reaction is, as already mentioned, 0.00004.

Table XII summarises the results at 32° after deducting the dark reaction.

TABLE XII.

Wave-length.	cycloHexane conc.	Chlorine conc.	Mean unimol. const.
436 $\mu\mu$	M/3	M/65	0.00221
404 $\mu\mu$	M/3	M/69	0.000637
366 $\mu\mu$	M/3	M/66	0.000557

Table XIII gives the temperature coefficients of the reaction at different wave-lengths.

TABLE XIII.

Wave-length	436 $\mu\mu$	404 $\mu\mu$	366 $\mu\mu$
Temp. coefficient ...	$\left(\frac{0.00221}{0.00180}\right)^2$	$\left(\frac{0.00637}{0.00561}\right)^2$	$\left(\frac{0.000657}{0.000494}\right)^2$
	= 1.50	= 1.29	= 1.26

for 10° interval,

The temperature coefficient thus increases in wave-length and is in accordance with the well-known ideas of Tolman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 2285).

Influence of Intensity on Reaction Rate.—A knowledge of the influence of intensity of incident radiation on the reaction rate is essential in order to arrive at any satisfactory mechanism of the reaction. Experiments were, therefore, performed at a lower intensity of light of wave-length $436\mu\mu$ at temperatures 27° and 32° . The intensity was varied by altering the distance of the lamp from the reaction cell. The higher intensity (Tables IX and XII) corresponded to a galvanometer deflection of 131 mm., the lower intensity to a deflection of 67 mm. The ratio of the incident intensities was thus 2.0.

Table XIV gives the reaction at lower intensity of $436\mu\mu$.

TABLE XIV.

Intensity of $436\mu\mu = 0.67$ Hefners-at-100 cm.

Time in mins.	N/200-Thiosulphate.	Unimol const.
0	12.3 c.c.	—
15	11.95	0.000833
35	11.50	0.000834
70	10.80	0.000807
115	10.0	0.000782
160	9.25	0.000774
		Mean 0.000806

The light reaction is thus 0.000768.

At a temperature of 32° and *cyclohexane* concentration of $M/3$ and chlorine $M/6$, the light reaction constant at the same intensity as Table XIV above 0.000907.

The ratio of the velocity constant at the two intensities

$$\left(\frac{0.00221}{0.000907} = 2.4, \text{ and } \frac{0.00180}{0.000768} = 2.36 \right) \text{ is, therefore, } 2.4.$$

The reaction is thus directly proportional to the intensity of incident radiation. The same relation was obtained by Wood and Rideal in the bromination of *cyclohexane* vapour (*loc. cit.*).

After-effect.—Since the reaction had a very large quantum efficiency it was expected that it would show quite an appreciable after-effect. Experiments, however, failed to detect any marked after-effect.

The Mechanism of the Reaction.—The main features of the reaction are the following:—(1) The photochemical reaction between cyclohexane and chlorine appears to be unimolecular with respect to chlorine. The value of the constant is directly proportional to the intensity of incident radiation. It is independent of the concentration of the chlorine and increases slightly as the concentration of the acceptor increases. The constant gradually falls off as the reaction progresses, and hydrochloric acid is without any influence. The quantum efficiency of the reaction is very large and increases with increase in frequency of the incident radiation. The reaction shows no induction period or appreciable after-effect.

A mechanism of reaction has got to be found which explains all the observed facts.

The primary action is the action of the absorbed quantum on the chlorine molecule. In the bromination of cyclohexane vapour where the quantum efficiency is unity and there is, therefore, no reaction chain and the reaction rate is found to be directly proportional to the intensity, Wood and Rideal favour the formation of excited bromine molecules rather than that of atoms.

The formation of excited chlorine molecules can scarcely explain the large quantum efficiency observed in this reaction. Moreover, the numerous experiments of Ghosh and his collaborators in this laboratory, of Bódenstein, Berthoud and the work of Franck leave no room for doubt that the primary action of a light quantum ($\lambda < 4785 \text{ \AA}$) on a halogen molecule is dissociation of the molecule into a normal and an excited atom. In the previous paper on the chlorination of cinnamic acid, this point has been considered in some detail.

It seems at first inconsistent with the hypothesis of formation of atoms that the reaction rate in a chain reaction should be directly proportional to the intensity of incident radiation rather than to its square-root. In what follows a chain reaction is indicated which explains all the observed facts.

The primary action of the light quantum ($\lambda < 4785 \text{ \AA}$) is

As already indicated in the chlorination of cinnamic acid the life of excited chlorine formed on absorption of light is very great and the

reverse reaction ($\text{Cl} + \text{Cl} \rightarrow \text{Cl}_2$) is, therefore, very slow and can be neglected compared with the other possible reactions.

The following chain reaction thus takes place:—

Reaction (4) explains the inhibiting action of the monochloro-substitution product. Indicating the respective velocity constants of the above reactions by k_1 , k_2 , k_3 , k_4 and k_5 , we shall deduce an expression for the rate of formation of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{Cl}$.

Since the absorption was small, the light absorbed equals $I_0[\text{Cl}_2]$ where I_0 is the intensity of incident radiation.

$$\frac{+d\text{Cl}}{dt} = k_1 I_0 [\text{Cl}_2] + k_3 [\text{H}][\text{Cl}_2] + k_4 [\text{H}][\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{Cl}]$$

$$\frac{-d\text{Cl}}{dt} = k_2 [\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}][\text{Cl}] + k_5 [\text{H}][\text{Cl}]$$

In the steady state these are equal.

$$\text{Again } \frac{+d\text{H}}{dt} = k_2 [\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}][\text{Cl}]$$

$$\frac{-d\text{H}}{dt} = k_3 [\text{H}][\text{Cl}_2] + k_4 [\text{H}][\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{Cl}] + k_5 [\text{H}][\text{Cl}]$$

In the steady state they are equal. We have then

$$\begin{aligned} 2k_1 I_0 [\text{Cl}_2] + k_3 [\text{H}][\text{Cl}_2] + k_4 [\text{H}][\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{Cl}] \\ = k_2 [\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}][\text{Cl}] + k_5 [\text{H}][\text{Cl}] \quad \dots \quad (\text{A}) \end{aligned}$$

$$k_3 [\text{H}][\text{Cl}_2] + k_4 [\text{H}][\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{Cl}] + k_5 [\text{H}][\text{Cl}] = k_2 [\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}][\text{Cl}] \dots (\text{B})$$

Subtracting (B) from (A) we have

$$[\text{Cl}] = \frac{k_1 I_0 [\text{Cl}_2]}{k_5 [\text{H}]} \quad \dots \quad (\text{C})$$

From (B) we have

$$[\text{H}] = \frac{k_2[\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}][\text{Cl}]}{k_3[\text{Cl}_2] + k_4[\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{Cl}] + k_5[\text{Cl}]} \quad \dots \quad (\text{D})$$

Now

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d[\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{Cl}]}{dt} &= k_2[\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}][\text{Cl}] - k_4[\text{H}][\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{Cl}] \\ &= k_2[\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}][\text{Cl}] \left\{ 1 - \frac{k_4[\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{Cl}]}{k_3[\text{Cl}_2] + k_4[\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{Cl}] + k_5[\text{Cl}]} \right\} \\ &= k_2[\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}][\text{Cl}] \left\{ \frac{k_3[\text{Cl}_2] + k_5[\text{Cl}]}{k_3[\text{Cl}_2] + k_4[\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{Cl}] + k_5[\text{Cl}]} \right\} \\ &= \frac{k_1 k_2 [\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}] I_0 [\text{Cl}_2]}{k_5} \cdot \frac{k_3 [\text{Cl}_2] + k_5 [\text{Cl}]}{k_2 [\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}] [\text{Cl}]} \quad \text{substituting for} \end{aligned}$$

$[\text{Cl}]$ and from (B).

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{k_1 I_0 [\text{Cl}_2]}{k_5 [\text{Cl}]} \times k_3 [\text{Cl}_2] + k_1 I_0 [\text{Cl}_2] \\ &= k_3 [\text{H}] [\text{Cl}_2] + k_1 I_0 [\text{Cl}_2]. \end{aligned}$$

Since $[\text{H}]$ is very small, $\frac{d[\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{Cl}]}{dt}$ or the rate of reaction will be mainly given by $k_1 I_0 [\text{Cl}_2]$. In other words the reaction should be unimolecular with respect to chlorine and the unimolecular constant should be directly proportional to the intensity of incident radiation. This has been realised in the experiments.

The slight accelerating effect of increase in concentration of the acceptor and the retarding action of the monochloro-substitution product becomes clear if we take into consideration the term $k_3[\text{H}]$

$[Cl_2]$. From (C) and (D) we have the following quadratic equation in $[H]$.

$$[H]^2 \{k_3 k_3 [Cl_2] + k_3 k_4 [C_6H_{11}Cl]\} + k_1 k_5 I_0 [Cl_2] [H]$$

$$- k_1 k_2 [C_6H_{12}] I_0 [Cl_2] = 0$$

or

$$[H] = \frac{-k_1 k_5 I_0 [Cl_2] \sqrt{\{k_1 k_5 I_0 [Cl_2]\}^2 + 4k_1 k_2 [C_6H_{12}] I_0 [Cl_2] \{k_3 k_3 [Cl_2] + k_3 k_4 [C_6H_{11}Cl]\}}}{2\{k_3 k_3 [Cl_2] + k_3 k_4 [C_6H_{11}Cl]\}}$$

It is clear from above that $[H]$ increases with increase in the concentration of the acceptor and diminishes as the concentration of chlorocyclohexane increases. Here is thus an explanation for the observed effect of the concentration of the acceptor and of the reaction product on the velocity of reaction. A complete theoretical explanation has thus been furnished for the experimentally observed facts.

The increase in quantum efficiency with increase in frequency can be explained in the same way as in the chlorination of cinnamic acid. With increase in frequency of the absorbed quantum ($\lambda < 4785 \text{ \AA}^\circ$) the kinetic energy of the atoms formed increases and this energy is communicated to the reaction products. The greater the frequency, the greater will be the energy of the products and consequently the longer the chain.

Photo-chlorination in Solutions.—This work as well as the previous one on the chlorination of cinnamic acid makes it abundantly clear that almost the same difficulties surround chlorination reactions in solution as in the gaseous state. The life of the excited chlorine appears to be very great in solution as well. The quantum efficiency, though not as great as in the combination of hydrogen and chlorine, is still considerably greater than unity showing complicated chain reactions. It is indeed remarkable that no induction period or after-effect could be detected in either of these reactions. In solution one disturbing and complicating factor is absent and that is oxygen.

Summary.

The photochemical reaction between *cyclohexane* and chlorine in carbon tetrachloride solutions has been studied in white as well as in monochromatic light. The reaction gives a unimolecular constant with respect to chlorine, that is independent of the concentration of chlorine and increases slowly with increase in concentration of the acceptor. The reaction constant is directly proportional to the intensity of incident radiation. The constant slightly falls off as the reaction progresses and hydrochloric acid is without any influence. The quantum efficiency is 19 at $436\mu\mu$, 30 at $404\mu\mu$ and 41 at $366\mu\mu$. The temperature coefficient is 1.5 at $436\mu\mu$, 1.29 at $404\mu\mu$ and 1.26 at $366\mu\mu$. An explanation of the observed facts is given and an expression for the reaction rate derived on the basis of the following mechanism : -

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